

NOTES

Kinetics of Reaction Between Iodoacetate and Thiosulphate Ions: Part-I

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There seems no work on record relative to measurement of velocities of reaction between iodoacetate and thiosulphate ions. The kinetics of reaction between thiosulphate and chloroacetate or bromoacetate ions have been investigated by Kappanna¹, La Mer² respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were either Analar or E Merck's guaranteed reagent quality. The iodoacetic acid was made by the action of potassium iodide on chloroacetic acid in dry acetone medium. The iodoacetic acid was converted into sodium iodoacetate by the method described by Kappanna and Patwardhan³. The salt is purified by recrystallisation and purity of salt is tested by the estimation of iodine.

The solutions of different concentrations were prepared by dissolving exact quantities of salt in conductivity water. As the aqueous solutions of iodine and thiosulphate change their strength on keeping for a long time, the solutions were prepared fresh before the experiments. These solutions are standardised before each days work. A thermostat was set at $20^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Two solutions, one containing iodoacetate and other thiosulphate were kept in a water thermostat for one hour and then mixed. Immediately known volume of reaction mixture was withdrawn by pipette into ice water and titrated against standard iodine solution. After certain intervals the same volumes of reaction mixture was withdrawn during the course of reaction and titrated as before. Ostwald's isolation method is used for determination of order of reaction. Each reactant is taken in large concentration in turn and order of reaction is determined with respect to other reactant.

TABLE I

Iodoacetate=0.01 M, Sodium Thiosulphate=0.001M, 50ml. reaction titrated each time
N
against — iodine solution.
200

Time in minutes	Volume of titrant required in ml	$0.434 K = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
1. 0	10.0	—
2. 60	7.6	0.001986 min ⁻¹
3. 100	6.4	0.001938 „
4. 150	5.1	0.001962 „
5. 200	4.1	0.001936 „
6. 250	3.3	0.001926 „
7. ∞	0	mean 0.00195 min ⁻¹

1. A. N. Kappanna, *This Journal*, 1928, 5, 293.2. V. K. La Mer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 3341.3. A. N. Kappanna, and H. W. Patwardhan, *This Journal*, 1932, 9, 379.

TABLE II

Iodoacetate = .001 M, Hypo = 01 M, 50 ml of reaction mixture titrated against
 $\frac{N}{20}$ iodine solution.

No.	Time in minutes	Volume of titrant required	$0.434 K = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
1.	0	10.0 ml.	—
2.	40	9.8	0.002422 min ⁻¹
3.	95	9.6	0.002356 „
4.	170	9.4	0.00238 „
5.	300	9.2	0.00233 „
6.	∞	9.0	mean 0.00237 „

from table I and II it is clear that the total order of reaction is found to be two being unity with respect to each reactant. So the velocity constant of the reaction is determined taking both reactants in equimolar quantities and velocity constant of reaction is calculated

by the classical equation $K = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$

where t stands for time in minutes, a, for initial concentrations of reactants and x is change in the concentration of reactants.

TABLE III

Iodoacetate = $\frac{M}{200}$ and hypo = $\frac{M}{200}$ 10 ml of the reaction mixture titrated each time
 against $\frac{N}{100}$ iodine solution

No.	Time in minutes	Volume of titrant	$K = \frac{1}{t} x \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$
1.	0	5.0 ml	—
2.	100	4.0 „	0.500 mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
3.	200	3.3 „	0.501 „
4.	400	2.5 „	0.500 „
5.	600	2.0 „	0.500 „
6.	∞	0.0 „	mean 0.500 „

TABLE IV

Iodoacetate = $\frac{M}{400}$ Hypo = $\frac{M}{400}$ 20 ml of the reaction mixture titrated each time
 against $\frac{N}{100}$ iodine solution.

No.	Time in minutes	Volume of titrant	$K = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$
1.	0	5.0 ml	—
2.	100	4.5 „	0.440 M mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
3.	200	4.1 „	0.439 „
4.	350	3.6 „	0.444 „
5.	500	3.2 „	0.444 „
6.	600	3.0 „	0.450 „
7.	∞	0.0 „	mean 0.443 „

Fairly constant values are obtained for second order rate constant when the reactants are taken in equimolar quantities by graphical method, differential method, half change method and method suggested by Wilkinson⁴. This confirms that the reaction is of second order. By table III and IV it is found that the rate constant goes on decreasing with decreasing concentrations of reactants. It may be due to primary salt effect and so it is necessary for doing the work at other ionic strength and the results are shown as given in table V.

TABLE V

Ionic strength μ	.02	.01	.008	.005	.0025
K in mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	0.500	0.443	0.425	0.384	0.357

From the above table $\frac{d \log K}{d \sqrt{\mu}}$ is calculated and is found to be 2 below ionic strength $K = .01$ obeying Debye-Hückel equation.

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4. R. W. Wilkinson, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, **39**, 1395.